

CLINICAL TRIAL PROTOCOL

**Effect of individualized blood pressure management on
postoperative outcomes in hypertensive patients undergoing
major surgery**

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Ethics Approval: Osaka Metropolitan University Graduate School of Medicine Ethics Committee
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1. Synopsis

Item	Description
Study title	Effect of individualized blood pressure management on postoperative outcomes in hypertensive patients undergoing major surgery
Design	Investigator-initiated, two-center, patient-blinded, parallel-group randomized controlled trial (1:1 allocation).
Setting	Two participating hospitals in Japan: Osaka Metropolitan University Hospital and Osaka City General Hospital.
Population	Adults (≥ 20 years) with treated hypertension undergoing elective abdominal surgery under general anesthesia expected to last ≥ 3 hours, with planned intraoperative invasive arterial blood pressure monitoring.
Interventions	Individualized group: maintain intraoperative mean arterial pressure (MAP) within $\pm 10\%$ of each patient's preoperative baseline MAP. Standard group: maintain intraoperative MAP ≥ 65 mmHg. Vasoactive agents and dosing at attending anesthesiologist's discretion.
Primary outcome	Postoperative acute kidney injury (AKI) within 7 days after surgery, defined by KDIGO criteria (serum creatinine and/or urine output).
Key secondary outcomes	AKI stage ≥ 2 within 7 days; initiation of renal replacement therapy within 7 days
Sample size	Target enrollment 400 patients (200 per group).
Analysis population	Modified intention-to-treat: all randomized patients who received the allocated intraoperative blood pressure management strategy.
Timeline	Planned recruitment start: September 2022. Planned study end: December 2026 (last follow-up and analysis).

Abbreviations: AKI, acute kidney injury; KDIGO, Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes; MAP, mean arterial pressure; RRT, renal replacement therapy.

2. Background and Rationale

Postoperative acute kidney injury (AKI) is a common and clinically important complication after major noncardiac surgery, particularly in older patients and those with pre-existing risk factors. Observational studies have shown associations between intraoperative hypotension (depth and duration) and postoperative AKI. These findings have motivated randomized trials evaluating intraoperative blood pressure targets and individualized strategies.

Patients with chronic hypertension may have altered autoregulatory thresholds and may be vulnerable to decreases in perfusion pressure. We therefore designed a pragmatic randomized trial to compare an individualized strategy targeting each patient's preoperative baseline MAP with a pragmatic standard strategy targeting MAP ≥ 65 mmHg, focusing on postoperative AKI within 7 days as the primary endpoint.

3. Objectives and Hypotheses

3.1 Primary objective

To determine whether individualized intraoperative blood pressure management (maintaining MAP within $\pm 10\%$ of preoperative baseline MAP) reduces the incidence of postoperative AKI within 7 days after elective abdominal surgery compared with standard management (maintaining MAP ≥ 65 mmHg) in adults with treated hypertension.

3.2 Secondary objectives

To compare groups with respect to: (1) AKI stage ≥ 2 within 7 days; (2) initiation of renal replacement therapy within 7 days

3.3 Hypothesis

We hypothesize that individualized intraoperative blood pressure management will reduce the incidence of postoperative AKI compared with standard management.

4. Trial Design and Setting

This is an investigator-initiated, two-center, patient-blinded, parallel-group randomized controlled trial with 1:1 allocation to individualized or standard intraoperative blood pressure management.

The trial is conducted at Osaka Metropolitan University Hospital and Osaka City General Hospital in Japan. Written informed consent is obtained during the preoperative outpatient anesthesia assessment.

After enrollment is completed, patients are randomly assigned in a 1:1 ratio to the individualized or standard intraoperative blood pressure management group. The randomization sequence is generated before study initiation by an independent investigator not involved in intraoperative anesthetic management.

Patients are blinded to group assignment. Attending anesthesiologists are aware of the allocated strategy. Outcome data extraction and AKI staging are performed by investigators blinded to treatment allocation.

5. Participant Selection

5.1 Inclusion criteria

Participants must meet all of the following criteria:

- - Age ≥ 20 years.
- - Scheduled for elective abdominal surgery under general anesthesia expected to last ≥ 3 hours.
- - Documented diagnosis of hypertension and treatment with at least one antihypertensive medication at the preoperative outpatient visit.
- - Planned intraoperative invasive arterial blood pressure monitoring.

5.2 Exclusion criteria

Participants meeting any of the following criteria are excluded:

- - Emergency surgery.
- - Planned postoperative tracheal intubation at the end of surgery.
- - Preexisting renal dysfunction (estimated glomerular filtration rate < 30 mL/min/1.73 m²).
- - Renal surgery.
- - Procedures for which the attending anesthesiologist anticipates the need for deliberate hypotension (e.g., aortic aneurysm surgery).
- - Preoperative baseline ward MAP < 75 mmHg (defined as the arithmetic mean of all ward blood pressure measurements from hospital admission until immediately before surgery).

6. Study Procedures and Interventions

6.1 Preoperative management

Baseline MAP is defined as the arithmetic mean of all ward blood pressure measurement values recorded in the electronic medical record from hospital admission until immediately before surgery.

Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors and angiotensin II receptor blockers are discontinued 24 hours before surgery. All other antihypertensive medications are continued up to the time of surgery.

6.2 Intraoperative monitoring

Before induction of general anesthesia, an appropriately sized upper-arm cuff is applied, and noninvasive blood pressure is measured at 5-minute intervals.

After induction, an arterial catheter is inserted into the radial artery and connected to a disposable pressure transducer. The transducer is positioned at the level of the right atrium and zeroed to atmospheric pressure.

6.3 Blood pressure targets

Participants are randomized to one of the following intraoperative blood pressure management strategies:

- - Individualized group: maintain intraoperative MAP within +/-10% of the preoperative baseline MAP.
- - Standard group: maintain intraoperative MAP \geq 65 mmHg.

The choice and dosing of vasoactive agents are left to the discretion of the attending anesthesiologist. General anesthesia is maintained with volatile anesthetics, targeting a bispectral index value of 40-60.

6.4 Data collection

The following data are collected from routinely available sources (electronic medical record and anesthesia information management system):

- Baseline demographics and comorbidities (including treated hypertension and antihypertensive medications).
- Surgical and anesthetic characteristics (procedure type, duration, use of epidural analgesia, ICU/high-dependency unit admission).
- Intraoperative blood pressure values (noninvasive and invasive), vasoactive agent use and doses, administered fluids and blood products, estimated blood loss, and urine output.
- Postoperative serum creatinine values and urine output (when a urinary catheter is in place) through postoperative day 7, and initiation of renal replacement therapy.

7. Outcomes

7.1 Primary outcome

The primary outcome is postoperative AKI within 7 days after surgery, defined according to the KDIGO criteria

7.2 Secondary outcomes

Prespecified secondary outcomes include:

- - Incidence of AKI stage \geq 2 within 7 days after surgery.
- - Initiation of renal replacement therapy (intermittent hemodialysis or continuous hemodiafiltration) within 7 days after surgery.

7.3 Outcome ascertainment

Postoperative serum creatinine measurements are obtained as part of routine clinical care. Patients without postoperative creatinine measurements within the 7-day observation window are excluded from the corresponding analyses.

Outcome data (serum creatinine and urine output) are extracted from the electronic medical record by investigators who are blinded to treatment allocation during data collection and AKI staging.

8. Safety Reporting

Both blood pressure management strategies are within the range of routine perioperative care. No investigational drugs or devices are used.

Serious adverse events (SAEs) are recorded and reported in accordance with institutional policies and applicable regulations. Any unexpected events judged by investigators to be possibly related to the intervention are reviewed by the study leadership and reported to the ethics committee as required.

9. Data Management and Confidentiality

Study data are collected from the electronic medical record and anesthesia information management system and recorded in a secure research dataset. Participants are assigned a unique study identification number. A re-identification key is stored separately with restricted access.

Electronic study data are stored on password-protected systems accessible only to authorized study personnel. Data sharing between participating sites, when necessary, is performed using secure institutional methods. Data are retained for the period specified by institutional policy and then destroyed securely.

10. Statistical Considerations

10.1 Sample size determination

Based on a previous report, we assumed an expected incidence of postoperative AKI of 27% in the standard-management group. We hypothesized that individualized blood pressure management would reduce the incidence of AKI to 13%. Using a two-sided test with $\alpha = 0.05$ and 90% power, the required sample size was calculated to be 184 patients per group. To account for potential dropouts and exclusions, the target enrollment was set at 400 patients.

10.3 Statistical methods

Between-group comparisons for continuous variables use the Wilcoxon rank-sum test.

The primary outcome (any AKI within 7 days) is compared between groups using the chi-squared test. For binary outcomes, Fisher's exact test is used when appropriate.

All tests are two-sided, and $P < 0.05$ is considered statistically significant.

11. Quality Assurance and Monitoring

Protocol adherence is supported by standardized written instructions. Data extraction and outcome adjudication are performed by trained investigators blinded to treatment allocation.

12. Ethical Considerations

The trial is conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and applicable ethical and regulatory requirements. Written informed consent is obtained from all participants prior to enrollment. Participant confidentiality is protected by use of study identifiers and restricted access to identifiable information.

This study evaluates blood pressure management strategies that are routinely used in perioperative practice, and participants are not exposed to additional invasive procedures beyond standard care for the planned surgery and monitoring.

13. Publication Policy

The investigators intend to publish the results in a peer-reviewed journal. Authorship and publication decisions follow institutional and international guidelines.

Appendix A. KDIGO AKI Criteria and Staging

KDIGO staging (highest stage within 7 days):

- - Stage 1: SCr 1.5-1.9 times baseline OR ≥ 0.3 mg/dL increase; urine output < 0.5 mL/kg/h for 6-12 hours.
- - Stage 2: SCr 2.0-2.9 times baseline; urine output < 0.5 mL/kg/h for ≥ 12 hours.
- - Stage 3: SCr 3.0 times baseline OR increase to ≥ 4.0 mg/dL OR initiation of RRT; urine output < 0.3 mL/kg/h for ≥ 24 hours OR anuria for ≥ 12 hours.

Appendix B. Schedule of Assessments

A suggested schedule of assessments is summarized below. In this pragmatic trial, some postoperative laboratory testing beyond postoperative day 1 is performed at clinician discretion.

Assessment	Outpatient visit (screening/consent)	Hospital admission to pre-op	Intraoperative period	Post-op days 1-7
Eligibility assessment	X	X		
Informed consent	X			
Baseline ward BP collection for baseline MAP		X		
Randomization		X		
Assigned MAP target applied			X	
Intraoperative BP capture and processing			X	
Serum creatinine				Mandatory POD1; additional as clinically ordered
Urine output (if catheter)				As available
AKI staging				X (up to day 7)
Renal replacement therapy				X (up to day 7)